

STRONG CONSTRAINTS ON $Z > 7$ GALAXIES WITH THE NEW CODE PEGASE.3 WITH DUST

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MAIN QUESTIONS ON FIRST GALAXIES

- What signatures to identify FIRST galaxies? then to derive star formation history, reionization epoch, link with dark haloes, link with AGN-BHs, ...
- **The new published model of spectrochemical galaxy evolution PEGASE.3** (Fioc & Rocca-Volmerange, 2019, AA), the role of dust.
- **The $z > 7$ observations-Best-fits with PEGASE templates-limits-Future**

WHAT SIGNATURES FOR « FIRST » GALAXIES ?

- **Ly α emission line (1215Å) galaxies trace only current starbursts in no metal-rich or dusty media because Ly α is a resonance line**
- **Ly Break (912Å) galaxies (LBG), yes (see H-dropouts, the talk of Wang) but need confirmation with high spectral resolution observations.**
- **AGN/Black hole environments, radiogalaxies (RoCCA-V et al, 2013), and galaxies in protoclusters (this conference)**
- **Ages from far-UV to near-IR energy distributions (for example with Pégase.2), only after metal dependence dust correction**

To identify First Galaxies

**Evolution signatures (break continuum and ionized gas emission lines)
from The synthetic far-UV to far-IR spectral energy distributions with dust
(synthetic SED templates) from the new spectrochemical code Pégase.3**

PART I.

The new code PÉGASE.3

Fioc and Rocca-Volmerange, A&A, 623, 143

+ Documentation and complements: [2019arXiv190202198](https://arxiv.org/abs/2019arXiv190202198) →

- Continuous UV-to-IR/submm spectral and chemical evolution of galaxies with Draine grains and dust modeling following

1) metal abundances

2) Dwek model

- with attenuation/emission energy balance by Monte Carlo simulations
- for spiral and spheroidal geometries, ISM diffuse and clumps.

- Star Formation, evolution and death of stars, gas, metals and dust
- Synthetic UV-farIR and submm SED for multiple scenarios
- Yields and abundances of metals in the interstellar medium (ISM),
- (recent) Nebular emission with metallicity from ionization equilibrium (CLOUDY)

The PÉGASE code of spectrochemical evolution of galaxies

Version 3.0.1

PÉGASE

Programme d'Étude des GALaxies par Synthèse Évolutive

Documentation and complements

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THE SYSTEM OF PEGASE MODEL

www.iap.fr/pegase → Code PÉGASE.3

Scenario of evolution: 4 parameters

1. Star Formation law $SFR(t)$
2. Inflow-time-scale
3. Outflows – winds in the IGM
4. Initial mass function IMF

Normalized total mass

INFALL, WINDS=f(t)
Multiple Initial GAS RESERVOIRS

Outflows towards IGM

One example of continua and emission lines (SED) from stars, ionized gas and dust of the Milky-Way like @ 13 Gyrs with PEGASE.3 :

**(FOLLOWING) ONE EXAMPLE OF THE MILKY-WAY LIKE @ 13 GYRS WITH PEGASE.3:
SILICATE GRAIN SEDS (LEFT) AND TEMPERATURE (RIGHT) FOR VARIOUS
SIZES :**

New developments (in progress for mock catalogs)

I. Tables of synthetic photometry colors for distant galaxies $=f(z)$ for spirals and spheroidals :
for the instrument filters of the telescopes Gaia, WISE, JWST and others

Galaxie elliptique											
z	JWST						WISE				G_gaia
	F090W	070-090	200-770	115-560	090-356	070-277	W1	W2	W3	W4	
99.999	99.999	99.999	99.999	99.999	99.999	99.999	19.013	2.605	0.676	-0.095	99.999
15.626	5.407	4.986	1.095	10.686	3.884	8.958	-1.118	-1.970	-4.595	-6.472	15.099
10.307	6.421	4.940	1.623	3.106	4.246	8.832	-0.381	-1.822	-4.448	-6.254	13.254
7.8692	5.464	6.438	2.471	3.044	3.414	8.869	-0.381	-1.646	-4.199	-5.349	8.438
6.4247	5.581	2.012	2.793	3.419	3.518	4.709	-0.465	-1.431	-3.897	-4.754	7.694
4.2038	5.646	1.016	2.178	4.154	3.321	3.974	-0.217	-1.277	-3.208	-3.851	7.073
2.5625	6.048	0.949	1.039	3.315	3.508	4.027	0.003	-0.859	-1.988	-2.841	7.178
1.2254	5.673	1.753	-0.487	1.061	2.361	3.960	0.727	0.231	-0.082	-0.288	7.644
0.95526	5.409	1.670	-0.868	0.545	1.817	3.428	0.960	0.748	0.413	0.226	7.187
0.74709	5.347	1.308	-1.137	0.189	1.386	2.828	1.290	1.274	0.881	0.708	6.872
0.4414	5.326	0.760	-1.583	-0.449	0.537	1.756	2.062	1.893	1.634	1.528	6.448
0.22227	5.419	0.554	-1.999	-1.046	0.014	1.041	2.724	2.432	2.264	2.186	6.277
0.05											

New developments of the code PEGASE.3 (present):

II. Absorption by the InterGalactic Medium , done

III. Facilities for Pegase3 python access, done

IV. Best-fit procedure, done (ask to Pegase members)

A constraint : To check the validity of the selected scenarios at $z=0$

The comparison of $z=0$ SDSS data (black dots) with predictions (colors)

of various PÉGASE scenarios SFR(z) (Rocca_Volmerange et al., 2015, ApJL, 803, L8)

**scenarios
SFR(z),**

PART II. SUCCESSIVE ANALYSES OF DISTANT GALAXIES WITH THE CODE PEGASE

II.1 The discovery of massive high-z galaxies from the K-band HUBBLE diagram limit (Rocca-Volmerange et al, 2004)

Predictions of high-z Pegase models **Red line=Masses $10^{12} M_{\text{sun}}$**

Observations: Deep field from HDF, Hawaii and RG, compilation by De Breuck et al, 2000

At z=4, radio galaxies are hosted by Ellipticals but Not spiral models

II.2 Best-fits of distant 3CR radiogalaxies with UV-optical-IR Pégase SED templates and AGN models

Ex: The radio galaxy 4C41.17 ($z=3.8$): 3 components

- **YOUNG** at age 30Myrs (full blue line)
- **EVOLVED Elliptical** at age 700Myrs (full red line)
- **AGN (600K, dashed green line)**

Excellent $\chi^2=0.96$, huge masses $10^{11} M_{\odot}$, low Z

Rocca-Volmerange et al, 2013, Drouart et al, 2016,

(FOLLOWING) THE CASE 1 < Z < 3 3CR RADIOGALAXIES (PODIGACHOSKI ET AL, 2016) : CONFIRMATION OF 2 STELLAR (YOUNG AND OLD) COMPONENTS WITH THE AGN SIEBENMORGEN MODEL.

PART II.3 THE $Z > 7$ GALAXIES WITH PEGASE.3

- **Observations** : The selection from « Super eighth » galaxies (Bridge et al, 2019) of 3 galaxies with a Spitzer {3.6-4.5} μ filter excess by Roberts-Borsani et al, 2016
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- **Successive Interpretations**
 - 1st interpretation: Starburst (Roberts-Borsani et al, 2016, Bridge et al, 2019) from OIII+H β lines
 - 2nd interpretation: Balmer Break (Rocca-Volmerange et al, 2018 [arXiv181204283R](https://arxiv.org/abs/1812.04283))
 - 3rd interpretation: Both stellar break and emission lines, (Rocca-Volmerange, B.; Hilberer, A.; Poupard, P. Fioc, submitted)

OBSERVATIONS

(ULTRA-VISTA, MCCrackEN ETAL, 2012, ASHBY ETAL. 2013, SMIT, 2015, ROBERTS-BORSANI ETAL., 2016)
 FROM UNUSUALLY BRIGHT GALAXIES FROM HST AND SPITZER CANDELS,
 SELECTED FOR THEIR RED IRAC/SPITZER COLOR (3.6)-(4.5)MU IN THE EGS FIELD: .

NOTE: KECK MOSFIRE SPECTROSCOPY REPORTED FOR 2 SOURCES AT Z=7.73 PM0.0006 AND 8.683P0.001M0.004

Selected from their typical Spitzer 3.6-.4.5 feature

The super-eight galaxy sample
 (Bridge et al, 2019)

Figure 10 from Newly Discovered Bright z=9-10 Galaxies and Improved Constraints on Their Prevalence Using the Full CANDELS Area
 null 2019 APJ 880 25 doi:10.3847/1538-4357/ab24c5
<http://dx.doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/ab24c5>
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Figure 4. Left: best-fit SED models (blue line) to the observed HST + Spitzer/IRAC + ground-based photometry (red points and error bars) for the four especially bright ($M_{UV,app} < -25.5$) $z > 7$ galaxies selected using our IRAC red selection criteria $(3.6) - (4.5) > 0.5$. Also included in the figure is the redshift estimate for the best-fit model SED provided by EAZY. Right: redshift likelihood distributions $P(z)$ for the same 4 candidate $z > 7$ galaxies, as derived by EAZY. The impact of the Spitzer/IRAC photometry on the redshift likelihood distributions should be close.

FIRST INTERPRETATIONS: A CURRENT STARBURST

1. Smit et al, 2015, 2016, Bouwens et al. 2016

with an instantaneous StarBurst ISB , assumed at a so high z:

But evidence of evolution with metals (OIII, etc) and: the interpretation with models of emission lines EW (OIII and Hbeta) is not consistent with continuum models (BC2003) without yields and no dust attenuation/emission

2 Roberts-Borsani et al. 2016 :

CANDELS data that show quite red IRAC [3.6]-[4.5] colors, filters are covering strong [O iii]+H β lines in the 4.5 μ m band. Interpreted with **SED templates @ 0.2 Z_e metallicity from the sum of Evolutionary Synthesis Models (GALEV, Kotulla et al. 2009)) added with the Nebular emission lines (Anders & Fritze-von Alvensleben, 2003)** BUT **No consistence of the continuous and emission line models, no chemical evolution .**

3. Bridge et al, 2019, The super-eight galaxies :Observations Models (evolution not compatible with Lyman α emissions) , Same remarks as previously

2ND INTERPRETATION: BALMER BREAK

IN FACT : TO FOLLOW EVOLUTION: CCSNE / SUPERNOVAE ENRICHMENT →

METALS → DUST → ATTENUATION IN THE FAR-UV CONTINUUM

BALMER BREAK BUT NO EMISSION LINES

(ROCCA ET AL. 2018, ARXIV): THE BEST FITS JUSTIFY DISCONTINUITY IN AGREEMENT WITH AGE-Z
→ MASSIVE AND EVOLVED GALAXY

3rd Interpretation: Stellar break **AND** emission lines (Rocca-Volmerange et al, 2019, submitted)

The best procedure of data best-fitting: synthetic SEDs with coherence of attenuated continua (star, ionized gas) and emission lines as OIII+ Hbeta lines with attenuation, possible with the published version of Pegase.3

EGSY-2008532660

predicted z versus spectroscopic z
 mature galaxy :Age 450 Myrs,
 galaxy mass : $10^{11} M_{\odot}$, $Z=0.01$
 Type spheroidal.

As shown in the submitted version,
 2 OTHER Galaxies at $z > 7$
 confirm this interpretation,

AND THE MOST DISTANT GALAXY GN-Z11 DISCOVERED AT Z= 11.1 AT 13.4 BILLION YEARS NO LINES BUT ALREADY MASSIVE AND EVOLVED!

Rocca-Volmerange, et al, submitted Observations: red crosses (Oesch et al 2016)
MODEL: blue line PEGASE.3 elliptical templates (Fioc & Rocca-Volmerange, 2019 www.iap.fr/pegase)

MAIN RESULTS

- **The red 3.6/4.5 micron color excess** predicted by **both stellar break and emission lines** constrains the evolved star formation scenario : ages and masses of $z > 7$ galaxies (submitted)
- **Galaxy type** : Only spheroidal geometry from MONTECARLO SIMULATIONS ARE VALID, current starburst are unlikely because metal abundances . Disk geomery is not accepted
- **Galaxy mass**: already 10^{11} Msun at $z=8-9$, galaxies are evolved
- **Galaxy ages** : @ $z=8$, 450-500 Myrs (Spheroid model), galaxies are evolved
- **Coherent with galaxy @ $z=11.1$, 160 Myrs (Spheroid model),**

Future

- **In development: better spectral/spatial resolution observations**
- **with ALMA, Gaia, WISE**
- **and the future telescopes JWST and EUCLID**
-
- **The epoch of formation z_{for}**
- **The activation of the Star formation process and AGN**
- **from models and observations of high- z proto-clusters**
- **Counts and Statistics with Luminosity or mass Functions at $z > 7$**

THE TOOL BOX PEGASE

WWW.IAP.FR/PEGASE

PEGASE.2 8 spectral types (Ell→Irr) for evolutionary UV-nearIR SED synthesis with Metals, Dust and geometrical effects

(Fioc & Rocca-Volmerange, 1997)

(+a version with higher spectral resolution, near submission, see below)

free access

free access

DE Z-PEG

Photometric redshifts

(Le Borgne & Rocca-Volmerange, 2002)

NEB-PEG

Nebular emission

PEGASE+CLOUDY+MAPPIN
GSIII

(Moy & Rocca-V, 2001, 2002)

PEGASE-HR (R= 10000), High spectral resolution with ELODIE library

Le Borgne, Rocca-Volmerange B., Lançon A. , Prugniel P. , Soubiran C. , 2004,

PEGASE.3 from farUV to far-IR/summ (stars, gas, metals + grains)
Fioc, Rocca-Volmerange, 2019 A&A
+ documentation(arXiv)

A new spectral library:

PegaseHR2, on Gaia domain, higher resolution near publication